

Mesopotamian Exorcistic Texts

By Adam Howe, University of Cambridge

Entry tags: Mesopotamian Religions, Religious Group, Assyrian Religions, Babylonian Religions, Text, Sumerian Text, Ancient Mesopotamian Text, Ritual text

The corpus of Mesopotamian exorcist texts consists of Sumerian and Akkadian incantations and ritual instructions that were intended to expel evil, heal illness, and protect people and property. The texts were composed and employed by practitioners known as the 'exorcist' (Akkadian *āšipu* or *mašmaššu*), and the corpus could be referred to in Akkadian as *āšipūtu* 'lore of the exorcist'. The earliest incantations date to the pre-Sargonic period (c. 2500 BCE onwards) and precursors of later standard incantations are known from the Ur III and Old Babylonian periods (c. 2100–1500 BCE). The process of canonization and standardization began in Babylonian in the late second millennium BCE, while many texts were grouped into standard series and copied in large numbers under the Sargonid kings of Assyria (8th–7th centuries BCE). Exorcistic texts continued to be copied in temples, school contexts, and private houses in the second half of the first millennium, until the Seleucid and Parthian periods (c. 330 BCE–50 CE). The corpus includes rituals against witchcraft, demons, and ghosts, medical texts, purification rites for people and buildings, and texts concerning *materia magica*, as well as parallel text production including commentaries and catalogues. The incantations consist of prayers to deities (whose participation was essential to the success of the rituals), addresses to sources of evil and *materia magica*, and explanations of accompanying ritual actions. The rituals make use of symbolic actions to destroy or expel evil, including manipulation of figurines representing the patient or source of evil, or the transfer of impurities to animal (or rarely human) substitutes. These were often accompanied by purification rites, prophylactic measures, and offerings to deities or sources of evil. The exorcist was also responsible for a number of medical treatments, including diagnosing the causes of illness, and preparing and administering medicines.

Date Range: 2500 BCE - 50 CE

Region: Ancient Mesopotamia

Region tags: Syria, Iraq

A rough map of the ancient Near Eastern region of Mesopotamia.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: D. Schwemer, 2011. 'Magic Rituals: Conceptualization and Performance' in K. Radner and E. Robson, eds. *The Oxford Handbook of Cuneiform Culture*. Oxford; New York: Oxford University Press, pp. 418–442.
- Source 2: D. Schwemer, 2015. 'The Ancient Near East' in D.J. Collins, S.J., ed. *The Cambridge History of Magic and Witchcraft in the West From Antiquity to the Present*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, pp. 17–51.
- Source 3: M.J. Geller, 2018. 'The Exorcist's Manual (KAR 44)' in U. Steinert, ed. *Assyrian and Babylonian*

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.phil.uni-wuerzburg.de/cmawro/corpus-of-mesopotamian-anti-witchcraft-rituals-online/>
- Source 1 Description: Website of the Corpus of Mesopotamian Anti-Witchcraft rituals, containing useful contextual essays and bibliography on magic and witchcraft in Mesopotamia

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/cmawro/corpus>
- Source 1 Description: Lemmatized transliterations and translations from the Corpus of Mesopotamian Anti-Witchcraft Rituals
- Source 2 URL: <https://seal.huji.ac.il/index.php/taxonomy/term/74>
- Source 2 Description: Transliterations and translations of some third and second millennium BCE incantations
- Source 3 URL: <https://ccp.yale.edu/catalogue?keys=&ccp=&cdli=&genre=4&findspot=All&date=All>
- Source 3 Description: Editions of ancient commentaries on magical texts

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

- No

Methods of Composition

- Impressed

Method of inscription

- Other [specify]: Stylus

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Clay

Clay object

- Clay tablet

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Impressed

Method of inscription

– Other [specify]: Stylus

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

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Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Field doesn't know

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: Sumerian was extinct as a spoken language by the time the exorcistic corpus was being standardized, but it continued to be used as an important literary language. It is not clear, however, whether it was regarded as a sacred language.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

Is it orally recited?

– Yes

- ↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Is it read?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?
 - Specify: Various

- ↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?
 - Yes

- ↳ On average, how many participants are present?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?
 - Yes

- ↳ On average, how many participants are present?
 - Number of participants: 2
 - Notes: For individual rituals, the texts usually refer to only the patient and the exorcist.

- ↳ How often do the rituals take place?
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: Some rituals took place on specific occasions while others were performed as needed.

- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are there synchronic practices?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– Field doesn't know

Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– Yes

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Notes: In general, no, but some incantations could be incorporated into amulets with prophylactic functions.

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Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

Notes: Some rituals seek to lift divine punishment for transgressions listed in incantations, many of which relate to cultic practice and social norms.

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– Yes

Notes: Negligence or improper practice in relation to cultic offerings could be punished by the gods.

↳ Libations?

– Yes

↳ Food?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Sacred objects?

– No

↳ Daily life objects?

– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Yes

↳ Food

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s)

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
 - Yes
 - Notes: Murder of e.g. family members is proscribed in lists of transgressions (and otherwise regulated by human legal systems), but it is not explicit about their membership of a religious group or polity.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
 - Yes
 - ↳ Adultery
 - Yes
 - ↳ Incest
 - Yes
 - ↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].
 - No
 - ↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)
 - No
 - Notes: Examples of abuse of power are included among lists of taboos, but not specifically in relation to sexual offences.
 - ↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?
 - No
 - ↳ Other sexual practices
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

Notes: Many of the transgressions listed in incantations like Shurpu relate to dishonesty.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

Notes: All transgressions against divine order are usually framed in terms of broken oaths (Akkadian *māmītu* 'oath, curse').

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

Notes: The practice of witchcraft is identified as a taboo in both anti-witchcraft rituals like *Maqlû* and rituals concerning divine punishment of transgressions like *Shurpu*.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– Yes

Notes: Washing rites are required before contact with the divine and during many of the exorcistic rituals, but this is more about ritual purity and the risk of contamination than 'personal hygiene'.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– I don't know

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

– Ritual list

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Notes: As a general rule, no, but a few texts are accompanied by inscribed drawings of the ritual set-up or demons mentioned in the text.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: Certain families of exorcists, sometimes identified with a semi-mythical ancestor, can be identified from the colophons of texts.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– Yes

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: Sexual abstinence was often required before entering into the presence of gods, but not specifically mentioned in any exorcistic rituals

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Social norms are generally considered part of the divinely ordained world order. Some distinctions, however, between violations regulated by human legal systems versus divine punishment (although both ultimately guaranteed by the gods).

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

Notes: Attack by demons, ghosts, and witches is sometimes related to loss of supernatural protection as a result of divine anger.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– Yes

Notes: The 'oath' or 'self-curse' (Akkadian *māmītu*) that regulates and punishes transgressions is sometimes personified and/or portrayed as a demon-like entity. Witches can also be agents of divine punishment, but they are often also portrayed as demons.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Notes: Although many of the relevant incantations express ignorance as to the exact nature of the transgression, this is probably a literary trope, and the patient's suffering at least identifies that they are subject to divine punishment.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

Notes: Attacks by demons or witches may seem random, but ultimately they require loss of divine protection which implies some sort of transgression having angered the gods.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

Notes: One's lot in the afterlife depends instead on the manner of death, including whether or not there was a proper burial, and on the descendants' adherence to proper offering practices.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Notes: Illness, changes in social position and economic success, and what we would regard as misfortune could all be attributed to divine anger resulting from some (often unknown) transgression.

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– No

Notes: We would regard some forms of suffering caused by divine punishment as bad luck, but Mesopotamians did not have similar notions of luck and misfortune, rather they were related to divine will and fate.

↳ Political failure?

– Yes

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Yes

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– Yes

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– Yes

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– Yes

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

↳ Sickness or illness?

– Yes

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– Yes

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– Yes

Notes: Divine punishment can affect other family members and even persist for seven generations of descendants (although the number itself is a literary trope).

↳ Other?

– Specify: Economic failure, disruption of normal social relations, inversion of hierarchies, etc.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: The exorcistic corpus is itself a collection of texts that forms part of the wider Mesopotamian scribal canon, although this is nowhere formally circumscribed.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Notes: In response to offerings, prayers, and proper ritual actions, the gods can lift the divine punishment and therefore reverse its ill effects. Exorcistic rituals are mostly about helping the patient out of bad situations, relieving suffering, healing illness, etc. rather than actively securing positive outcomes.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– I don't know

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Cremation?

– No

Notes: Representatives of witches are burnt so that they go up to the sky as smoke, implying that this could prevent someone from entering the netherworld. Additionally, burning is attested as a cause of death that could result in an evil ghost.

↳ Mummification?

– No

↳ Interment?

– Yes

Notes: Symbolic representations of source of evil can be buried in order that they become trapped in the netherworld.

↳ Cannibalism?

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying)?

– No

Notes: Being left unburied could result in a 'wandering' ghost, and such a fate is wished upon witches.

↳ Feeding to animals?

– No

Notes: Incantations against witches call for their corpses to be left unburied in the steppe and fed upon by dogs and vultures.

↳ Secondary burial?

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse?

– No

↳ Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?

– No

↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: Again, some food restrictions usually observed before entering into the presence of gods, but not specifically mentioned in exorcistic texts

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– Yes

Notes: When representations of ghosts or witches are buried, this is usually accompanied by real or model grave goods.

↳ Personal effects?

– No

↳ Valuable/precious items?

– No

↳ Other grave goods?

– Yes

Notes: Usually food and clothing as provisions for the journey to the netherworld.

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Notes: The representations are usually buried in a hole dug in the steppe specifically for the ritual and therefore with no formal ceremony or marker.

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Notes: One ritual involves a substitute king dying in place of the real king, in response to danger portended by a lunar eclipse, but none of the sources make clear how or even if the substitute king really died.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– No

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

Notes: If one is afflicted by the ghosts of family members, these can be appeased with food offerings or employed in the combat of evil ghosts.

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Notes: Various deities are of equal importance for the rituals, but especially Utu/Shamash, the sun god and divine judge, and father and son Enki/Ea and Asalluhi/Marduk, the gods of exorcism.

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts can 'seize' their victim or are described as being 'attached' to them.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward

– No

↳ Human spirits can punish

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts can pursue neglected funerary offerings.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– No

Notes: The nature of ghosts or of the suffering they cause can be connected to their cause of death, but this is probably not to do with memory.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts can cause visual and auditory disturbances in waking life and in dreams;

necromancy also practised in Mesopotamia.

↳ In waking, everyday life
– Yes

↳ In dreams
– Yes

↳ In trance possession
– No

↳ Through divination practices
– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists
– No

↳ Only through monarch
– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

↳ In trance possession?

– No

↳ Through divination practices?

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– I don't know

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– No

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

–Specify: Some deities take on specific roles in the rituals and/or their mythological background:
e.g. Shamash as divine judge, Enki/Ea as divine exorcist

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Gilgamesh (part-god, part-human) is invoked in the anti-witchcraft ritual Maqlû as judge of the netherworld

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?

– No

↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?

– I don't know

Notes: Gilgamesh is asked to enforce an oath against the witches, since they have violated social norms with their evil magic

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– I don't know

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Various demons and protective spirits are mentioned in the exorcistic texts

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: In general, divination in Mesopotamia was undertaken by specialists other than the exorcist, although they would have often worked together.

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Field doesn't know

Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some rituals are known to take place yearly or twice-yearly

Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– I don't know

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

Notes: See above for one possible exception

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– I don't know

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– No

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– Yes

Notes: Presumably, as offerings of incense and other burnt materials are common

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings?
(I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– I don't know

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Certain rituals provide stipulations about the place of performance, including location, prior purification, and the construction of special ritual structures. Otherwise, rituals could take place where required, and often at the client's home.

↳ Is it required?

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance)?

– Yes

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Notes: As a general rule, no, but a few texts are accompanied by inscribed drawings of the ritual set-up or demons mentioned in the text.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Field doesn't know

Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: The exorcistic corpus is itself a collection of texts that forms part of the wider Mesopotamian scribal canon, although this is nowhere formally circumscribed.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

– Ritual list

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: Certain families of exorcists, sometimes identified with a semi-mythical ancestor, can be identified from the colophons of texts.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– Yes

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– Field doesn't know

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Cremation?

– No

Notes: Representatives of witches are burnt so that they go up to the sky as smoke, implying that this could prevent someone from entering the netherworld. Additionally, burning is attested as a cause of death that could result in an evil ghost.

↳ Mummification?

– No

↳ Interment?

– Yes

Notes: Symbolic representations of source of evil can be buried in order that they become trapped in the netherworld.

↳ Cannibalism?

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying)?

– No

Notes: Being left unburied could result in a 'wandering' ghost, and such a fate is wished upon witches.

↳ Feeding to animals?

– No

Notes: Incantations against witches call for their corpses to be left unburied in the steppe and fed upon by dogs and vultures.

↳ Secondary burial?

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse?

– No

↳ Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?

– No

↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– Yes

Notes: When representations of ghosts or witches are buried, this is usually accompanied by real or model grave goods.

↳ Personal effects?

– No

↳ Valuable/precious items?

– No

↳ Other grave goods?

– Yes

Notes: Usually food and clothing as provisions for the journey to the netherworld.

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Notes: The representations are usually buried in a hole dug in the steppe specifically for the ritual and therefore with no formal ceremony or marker.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– No

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

Notes: If one is afflicted by the ghosts of family members, these can be appeased with food offerings or employed in the combat of evil ghosts.

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Notes: Various deities are of equal importance for the rituals, but especially Utu/Shamash, the sun god and divine judge, and father and son Enki/Ea and Asalluhi/Marduk, the gods of exorcism.

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts can 'seize' their victim or are described as being 'attached' to them.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward

– No

↳ Human spirits can punish

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts can pursue neglected funerary offerings.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– No

Notes: The nature of ghosts or of the suffering they cause can be connected to their cause of death, but this is probably not to do with memory.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts can cause visual and auditory disturbances in waking life and in dreams; necromancy also practised in Mesopotamia.

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

↳ In dreams

– Yes

↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life?
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams?
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession?
 - No
 - ↳ Through divination practices?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists?
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch?
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
 - Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
- Yes

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?
- Yes

- ↳ Organized hierarchically?
- Yes

- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific?
- No

- ↳ Other organization of pantheon?
- Specify: Some deities take on specific roles in the rituals and/or their mythological background:
e.g. Shamash as divine judge, Enki/Ea as divine exorcist

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Gilgamesh (part-god, part-human) is invoked in the anti-witchcraft ritual Maqlû as judge of the netherworld

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?
- No

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?
- No

- ↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?
- I don't know

Notes: Gilgamesh is asked to enforce an oath against the witches, since they have violated social norms with their evil magic

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Various demons and protective spirits are mentioned in the exorcistic texts

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: In general, divination in Mesopotamia was undertaken by specialists other than the exorcist, although they would have often worked together.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

Notes: Some rituals seek to lift divine punishment for transgressions listed in incantations, many of which relate to cultic practice and social norms.

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– Yes

Notes: Negligence or improper practice in relation to cultic offerings could be punished by the gods.

↳ Libations?

– Yes

↳ Food?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Sacred objects?

– No

- ↳ Daily life objects?
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
 - Yes
 - ↳ Food
 - Yes
 - ↳ Sacred space(s)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Sacred object(s)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about other
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
 - Yes
 - Notes: Murder of e.g. family members is proscribed in lists of transgressions (and otherwise regulated by human legal systems), but it is not explicit about their membership of a religious group or polity.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
 - Yes
 - ↳ Adultery
 - Yes
 - ↳ Incest

– Yes

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– No

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– No

Notes: Examples of abuse of power are included among lists of taboos, but not specifically in relation to sexual offences.

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– No

↳ Other sexual practices

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

Notes: Many of the transgressions listed in incantations like Shurpu relate to dishonesty.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

Notes: All transgressions against divine order are usually framed in terms of broken oaths (Akkadian *māmītu* 'oath, curse').

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

Notes: The practice of witchcraft is identified as a taboo in both anti-witchcraft rituals like Maqlû and rituals concerning divine punishment of transgressions like Shurpu.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
 - Yes
 - Notes: Washing rites are required before contact with the divine and during many of the exorcistic rituals, but this is more about ritual purity and the risk of contamination than 'personal hygiene'.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
 - I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

Notes: Attack by demons, ghosts, and witches is sometimes related to loss of supernatural protection as a result of divine anger.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– Yes

Notes: The 'oath' or 'self-curse' (Akkadian *māmītu*) that regulates and punishes transgressions is sometimes personified and/or portrayed as a demon-like entity. Witches can also be agents of divine punishment, but they are often also portrayed as demons.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Notes: Although many of the relevant incantations express ignorance as to the exact nature of the transgression, this is probably a literary trope, and the patient's suffering at least identifies that they are subject to divine punishment.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

Notes: Attacks by demons or witches may seem random, but ultimately they require loss of divine protection which implies some sort of transgression having angered the

gods.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

Notes: One's lot in the afterlife depends instead on the manner of death, including whether or not there was a proper burial, and on the descendants' adherence to proper offering practices.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Notes: Illness, changes in social position and economic success, and what we would regard as misfortune could all be attributed to divine anger resulting from some (often unknown) transgression.

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– No

Notes: We would regard some forms of suffering caused by divine punishment as bad luck, but Mesopotamians did not have similar notions of luck and misfortune, rather they were related to divine will and fate.

↳ Political failure?

– Yes

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Yes

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– Yes

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– Yes

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– Yes

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

↳ Sickness or illness?

– Yes

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– Yes

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– Yes

Notes: Divine punishment can affect other family members and even persist for seven generations of descendants (although the number itself is a literary trope).

↳ Other?

– Specify: Economic failure, disruption of normal social relations, inversion of hierarchies, etc.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Notes: In response to offerings, prayers, and proper ritual actions, the gods can lift the divine punishment and therefore reverse its ill effects. Exorcistic rituals are mostly about helping the patient out of bad situations, relieving suffering, healing illness, etc. rather than actively securing positive outcomes.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Social norms are generally considered part of the divinely ordained world order. Some distinctions, however, between violations regulated by human legal systems versus divine punishment (although both ultimately guaranteed by the gods).

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– I don't know

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: Sexual abstinence was often required before entering into the presence of gods, but not specifically mentioned in any exorcistic rituals

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: Again, some food restrictions usually observed before entering into the presence of gods, but not specifically mentioned in exorcistic texts

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Notes: One ritual involves a substitute king dying in place of the real king, in response to danger portended by a lunar eclipse, but none of the sources make clear how or even if the substitute king really died.

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– I don't know

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– I don't know

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some rituals are known to take place yearly or twice-yearly

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?
– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?
– I don't know

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?
– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?
– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?
– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?
– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?
– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?
– No

Notes: See above for one possible exception

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?
– I don't know

↳ Are there material offerings present?
– Yes

- ↳ Are they mandatory?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?
 - Yes

- ↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?
 - No

- ↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Presumably, as offerings of incense and other burnt materials are common

- ↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')
 - I don't know

- ↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Certain rituals provide stipulations about the place of performance, including location, prior purification, and the construction of special ritual structures. Otherwise, rituals could take place where required, and often at the client's home.

- ↳ Is it required?
 - No

- ↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance)?
 - Yes

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: There are rituals intended to secure success in battle.

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A city-state

– A nation-state

– An empire

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

Notes: Rituals to protect against field pests have a bearing on food production. Various food offerings are made to deities and other protective spirits, although the production of the offerings is not detailed in the ritual texts.

↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

↳ Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (E.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Most of our evidence for the training of exorcists and scribal training in general comes from private households and within families. Institutions like temples and the Library of Assurbanipal held copies of exorcistic texts, but it is unclear whether there was any formal training within the institutions.

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

– Other

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– Yes

Notes: Catalogues and colophons sometimes refer to the 'secrets of the exorcist', implying some conception of restricted knowledge. Exorcists were just one type of specialized scholar among several (physicians, diviners, astrologers, lamenters) whose work was connected to religious practice and were sometimes associated with temples, but were usually distinct from other cult practitioners (i.e. priests and other temple personnel).

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– Yes

Notes: See above.

Is education gendered according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Not explicitly mentioned, but all known exorcists are male and Mesopotamian scribal culture was male-dominated.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: See above.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– I don't know

Society & Institutions

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Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: There are rituals intended to secure success in battle.

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